

Hydrogen uptake behavior of Cr₂O₃ nanoparticle decorated f-MWCNTs at non-cryogenic temperatures

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Abstract: Cr₂O₃ nanoparticle decorated multiwalled carbon nanotubes (Cr₂O₃@f-MWCNTs) have been synthesized in different solvents such as water, triethylamine (TEA) and DMF. Morphology, functionalization, surface area, and hydrogen adsorption of prepared materials were examined through SEM with EDAX, TEM, BET analysis, FT-IR and adsorption isotherms. It has been found that solvents played important role in controlling uniform distribution of Cr₂O₃ nanoparticles on MWCNTs and uptake of hydrogen. After decorating the nanoparticles of Cr₂O₃ on carboxylate functionalized MWCNTs (f-MWCNTs), the hydrogen uptake capacity was enhanced from 0.1 to 0.52 wt% at 253 K and 0.06 to 0.45 wt% at 298 K.

Keywords: Pristine-MWCNTs, functionalization, metal decoration, hydrogen adsorption.

Introduction

Hydrogen is an ideal energy carrier which is considered for future automotive applications. However, the development of an effective and safe hydrogen storage system is a key enabling technology for on-board vehicle applications. The U.S. Department of Energy (DOE) established specific technical targets (6 wt% capacity at non-cryogenic conditions) for on-board hydrogen storage systems for hydrogen storage^{1,2}. The decoration of carbonaceous nanomaterials with the transition metals could strongly create numerous physisorption and chemisorption interactions³⁻⁹. As CNTs' inner, outer, and inter-tube regions offer wide surface areas, the possibilities for physisorption improves significantly. There is also great potential for chemisorption through the decoration of metals on the surface of CNTs¹⁰. Further, metal oxide nanoparticles can exhibit unique chemical properties due to their small size and high density of corner or edge surface sites^{1,2}. Chromium(III) oxide belongs to rhombohedral crystal system and is of great interest due to its wide range of applications such as heterogeneous catalyst¹¹, pigments to reflect

infrared radiation¹², solar energy application¹³, high temperature resistant materials (m.p. ≈2300°C)^{13,14} liquid crystal displays¹⁵, wear resistance¹⁶ and coating material¹⁷. Furthermore, different methods are available to prepare nanoparticles of Cr₂O₃ such as sol-gel technique¹⁸, sonochemical method¹⁹, precipitation-gelation²⁰, mechanochemical process²¹, microwave plasma²² and gas condensation²³, etc.

In this context, M. Polanski *et al.*, reported the nanocomposite of MgH₂ and Cr₂O₃ nanopowder²⁴. This nanocomposite chemisorb about 5.2 wt% hydrogen at 325°C. Similarly, R. Ud-din reported that the composite prepared from LiAlH₄ and Cr₂O₃ nanoparticles adsorb 1.9 wt% hydrogen at 175°C²⁵. Hydrogen storage capacity can be improved in decorating the MWCNT by Co, Fe, Ni, Ca metals²⁶ and nanoparticles of CuO, Fe₂O₃ and ZnO^{27,28}.

In the present study, we report the synthesis and hydrogen uptake behavior of Cr₂O₃ nanoparticle decorated f-MWCNTs prepared using water, trimethylamine (TEA) and DMF at non-cryogenic temperatures and moderate pressures.

Experimental

Materials:

All chemicals were of analytical grade and used without any further purification. $\text{Cr}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and triethylamine (TEA) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, dimethyl formamide (DMF) was procured from Merck India.

Purification and functionalization of MWCNTs:

Raw MWCNTs were purified by refluxing at 95°C for 6 h in 6.0 M HCl. Filtered solid was calcined in furnace at $500\text{--}520^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 h to get the pristine MWCNTs (p-MWCNTs). For carboxylate functionalization, 0.3 g of the p-MWCNTs in 150 ml of nitration mixture (1:3 HNO_3 and H_2SO_4) was refluxed for 48 h under magnetic stirring. The resulting solid was filtered and washed till to attain neutral pH. Further the sample was dried in vacuum at 40°C overnight to obtain COOH-MWCNTs (f-MWCNTs).

Preparation of $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3@f\text{-MWCNTs}$:

200 mg of carboxylate functionalized MWCNTs (f-MWCNTs) and 8.00 g (0.02 mol, high metal concentration (HMC)) or 4.00 g (0.01 mol, low metal concentration (LMC)) of $\text{Cr}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were taken in a 500 ml round bottomed flask. To this, 150 ml distilled water/150 ml distilled water containing 0.5 ml triethylamine (TEA)/150 ml dimethyl formamide (DMF) was mixed thoroughly and heated at 80°C for 6 h. The resulting solid was washed till the pH of the sample was 7.0 and dried overnight in vacuum at 40°C .

Characterization methods:

The texture/morphology of the obtained compounds was determined by Scanning Electron Microscopy (FEI quanta 200 FEG with EDS) and Transmission Electron Microscopy (Philips CM200). The IR spectrum of the sample was recorded on Perkin-Elmer (Spectrum two FT-IR) system using KBr pellet preparation method. The powder X-ray diffraction patterns were obtained on a Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer (45 Kv, 40 mA) with Ni filtered $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$). Hydrogen gas sorption measurements were carried out using a high-pressure gas adsorption system, BELSORP-HP.

Results and discussion

The hydrogen sorption properties of $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3@f\text{-MWCNTs}$ synthesized under different experimental conditions using water, triethylamine and DMF, in a two-step chemical synthesis route were examined. The carboxylate functionalized MWCNTs prepared from purified/pristine MWCNTs in the initial step and were decorated with nanoparticles of Cr_2O_3 in the second stage. Initially the pristine MWCNTs (p-MWCNTs) were purified and converted into carboxylate functionalized MWCNTs (f-MWCNTs) by chemical oxidation process. TEM images revealed that both morphology/texture and end-cap structure of carbon nanotubes with the average diameter of CNTs about 30 nm was well-reversed in f-MWCNTs (Fig. 1a). To identify the optimum conditions required for designing the materials with efficient hydrogen storage properties, a number of chemical reactions were conducted by changing the reacting media and the metal concentration for decorating the carboxylate functionalized MWCNTs. As shown in TEM and SEM images (Fig. 1b and 1c), nanoparticles of Cr_2O_3 about 5–10 nm in size are decorated on the surface of functionalized MWCNTs (f-MWCNTs). Elemental mapping and EDAX analysis of $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3@f\text{-MWCNTs}$ were shown in Fig. 1d and 1e. These results showing the Cr, C and O content from CNTs along with decorated metal. The above results showed that Cr_2O_3 nanoparticles were well-dispersed on MWCNTs with varying concentration of metal. The FT-IR spectrum of $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3@f\text{-MWCNTs}$ is shown in Fig. 2. The peaks at 3436 cm^{-1} and 1631 cm^{-1} are assigned to the stretching vibrations of O-H and C=O of carboxyl functional groups from $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3@f\text{-MWCNTs}$. The peak at 633 cm^{-1} corresponds to the Cr-O bond. The powder XRD pattern of $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3@f\text{-MWCNTs}$ is shown in Fig. 3. The diffraction peaks at 25.4 and 42.9° corresponding to the graphitic reflections (JCPDS No. 01-0646) and peaks at 18.13° , 27.6° and 34.2° correspond to Cr_2O_3 nanoparticles.

The hydrogen adsorption capacities of $\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_3@f\text{-MWCNTs}$ along with pristine and functionalized ones

Fig. 1. TEM images of (a) p-MWCNTs, (b) Cr₂O₃@f-MWCNTs, (c) SEM image of Cr₂O₃@f-MWCNTs, (d) SEM image of Cr₂O₃@f-MWCNTs with elemental mapping, (e) EDAX image of Cr₂O₃@f-MWCNTs.

Fig. 2. FT-IR spectra of (a) p-MWCNTs, (b) f-MWCNTs and (c) Cr₂O₃@f-MWCNTs.

(p-MWCNTs, f-MWCNTs) were measured volumetrically at 253 K and 298 K using high pressure sorption analyzer BELSORP-HP and at moderate pressures of 70 bar (Table 1). Hydrogen excess sorption isotherms for Cr₂O₃@f-MWCNTs prepared at different metal concentrations (high metal concentration (HMC) and low metal concentration (LMC)) in three different solvents, i.e., water, triethylamine (TEA) and DMF. As hydrogen adsorption was reversible in all the samples, the desorption curves

Fig. 3. Powder diffraction patterns of (a) p-MWCNTs and (b) Cr₂O₃@f-MWCNTs.

Table 1. Hydrogen uptake capacity of Cr₂O₃@f-MWCNTs

Sample	Reaction medium	H ₂ uptake at 253 K and 70 bar (wt%)	H ₂ uptake at 298 K and 70 bar (wt%)
p-MWCNTs	Water	0.30	0.12
f-MWCNTs	Water	0.12	0.06
Cr ₂ O ₃ @f-MWCNTs	Water	0.18 ^a	0.13 ^a
		0.31 ^b	0.22 ^b
Cr ₂ O ₃ @f-MWCNTs	Triethylamine	0.20 ^a	0.16 ^a
		0.46 ^b	0.31 ^b
Cr ₂ O ₃ @f-MWCNTs	DMF	0.31 ^a	0.17 ^a
		0.52 ^b	0.45 ^b

^aLMC = Low metal concentration, ^bHMC = High metal concentration.

have not been shown in figures. The excess sorption isotherms of all samples displayed a liner trend typical for monolayer adsorption on porous materials. It was observed that the hydrogen adsorption capacity of pristine and carboxylate functionalized MWCNTs at 253 K and 70 bar pressure are 0.3 and 0.1 wt%, respectively (Fig. 4). At 298 K the hydrogen adsorption capacity of pristine and f-MWCNTs are 0.12 and 0.06 wt%, respectively (Fig. 6). The decrease in hydrogen adsorption capacity from pristine to

Fig. 4. Hydrogen uptake by p-MWCNTs, f-MWCNTs and Cr_2O_3 @f-MWCNTs at 253 K at HMC.

Fig. 5. Hydrogen uptake by p-MWCNTs, f-MWCNTs and Cr_2O_3 @f-MWCNTs at 253 K at LMC.

functionalized MWCNTs at both temperatures is due to blocking of surface pores by COOH groups.

Cr_2O_3 @f-MWCNTs prepared at LMC in water, triethylamine, and DMF at 253 K adsorbs 0.18, 0.20, and 0.31 wt% of hydrogen (Fig. 5) whereas Cr_2O_3 @f-MWCNTs prepared at HMC adsorb 0.31, 0.46, and 0.52 wt% (Fig. 4) of hydrogen, respectively. EDAX analysis reveals that the amount of Cr decorated on surface of f-MWCNTs was 0.48 wt% at high metal concentration HMC. This result indicates that the hydrogen sorption properties are drastically increased on increasing the Cr_2O_3 nanoparticle content on surface of f-MWCNTs. Fig. 7 shows that the hydrogen adsorption isotherms recorded for Cr_2O_3 @f-

Fig. 6. Hydrogen uptake by p-MWCNTs, f-MWCNTs and Cr_2O_3 @f-MWCNTs at 298 K at HMC.

MWCNTs prepared at LMC in water, triethylamine and DMF at 298 K indicated 0.13, 0.16, 0.17 wt% adsorption. Similarly Cr_2O_3 @f-MWCNTs prepared at HMC in the above mentioned reaction conditions adsorbed 0.22, 0.31, and 0.45 wt% of hydrogen (Fig. 6).

Fig. 7. Hydrogen uptake by p-MWCNTs, f-MWCNTs and Cr_2O_3 @f-MWCNTs at 298 K at LMC.

From the aforementioned observations, Cr_2O_3 @f-MWCNTs prepared in water, triethylamine, and DMF media at low and high concentration of metal exhibited high adsorption capacities compared to pristine-MWCNTs and COOH-functionalized MWCNTs. The adsorption capacity remarkably increased at 253 K as compared to that observed at 298 K.

Conclusions

Cr₂O₃ nanoparticle decorated MWCNTs were prepared under different experimental conditions by varying the solvent and metal concentration. Solvent as well as metal content played a key role in higher uptake of hydrogen through modifying the sorption kinetics via spillover mechanism.

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